

COMPUTER-AIDED PHOTOELASTIC ANALYSIS OF ORTHOGONAL 3D TEXTILE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A computer-aided photoelastic analysis method developed for orthogonal three-dimensional (3D) textile composite material is presented. In this method a digital image processing technique is used to extract both the isochromatic and isoclinic parameters. A least square formulation with constraints constructed by Finite Element Method (FEM) is then applied to solve for strain and stress distributions over a region of interest. Those composites used in this study were fabricated by woven carbon fiber fabrics impregnated with epoxy resin. The spacing between neighboring fiber tows was as wide as 6 mm. A simple tension test was carried out for the analysis. The results show that the strain and stress fields obtained not only satisfy all the elasticity field equations for the homogenized composite material but also best fit the photoelastic data over the region in an averaging sense.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, three-dimensional (3D) textile composites have attracted a lot of interests due to their excellent through-thickness properties, damage tolerance and impact resistance [1-3]. Many theoretical and experimental studies have been carried out for 3D textile composites [4-7]. The flexural and axial compressive properties of 3D braided composite I-beam were investigated by Yau *et al* [4]. A Finite Element analysis was conducted on a double cantilever beam specimen of a 3D interlocked fabric composite by Byun *et al* [5]. The elastic constants of two-step braided composites were analyzed using a geometric model based on lamination analogy and stiffness averaging method by Byun *et al* [6]. The influence of weave structure on pin-loaded strength of orthogonal 3D composites were investigated with photoelasticity by Chen *et al* [7].

Orthogonal 3D textile composites are reinforced with a system of three straight, mutually orthogonal fiber tows. The spacing between neighboring tows is normally as wide as more than 2 mm. Strictly speaking, such composites can not be considered as homogeneous materials even in a macroscopic scale. However, either for analysis or in real applications homogenized properties of these composites are used for practical purposes.

Photoelastic analysis of orthogonal 3D textile composites is capable of yielding the whole-field isochromatic and isoclinic data. However, those photoelastic data vary locally according to the non homogeneous structure of the composites. Therefore, how to interpret those photoelastic data and use them to solve for the strains and stresses in terms of homogenized properties

becomes a serious task.

In this study we present a computer-aided photoelastic analysis method for orthogonal 3D textile composites. A digital image processing technique is developed in this paper to extract both isochromatic and isoclinic data over the entire region of the specimen using reflective photoelasticity. Then a least square method with constraints of force equilibrium equations constructed by Finite Element formulation using homogenized composite properties is employed to solve for strains and stresses in a region of interest. As a result, the strains and stresses obtained satisfy all the elasticity field equations and also best fit the photoelastic data over the region in an averaging sense.

DETERMINATION OF ISOCROMATIC AND ISOCLINIC PARAMETERS

PHOTOELASTICITY

In photoelasticity experiments both the circular and plane polariscopes are used to extract the isochromatic parameter R and isoclinic parameter α ; R is the relative angular phase retardation and α represents the angle of the major principal strain (or stress) direction.

For photoelastic analysis of orthogonal 3D textile composite materials a birefringent coating on the composite model is needed for reflection of light in a reflection polariscope. The strain-optic law for strain induced birefringence in the coating is:

$$R = \frac{4\pi t K}{\lambda} (\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2) \quad (1)$$

where t is the thickness of the birefringent coating, K is the strain-optical coefficient of the coating, λ is the wavelength of the light and ε_1 and ε_2 are the in-plane principal strains in the coating as well as in the model.

In a circular polariscope and a plane polariscope, of dark field setup, the intensity of the transmitted light emerging from the analyzer is respectively

$$I_1 = \kappa_c \sin^2 \frac{R}{2} \quad (2.1)$$

and

$$I_2 = \kappa_p \sin^2 2\alpha \sin^2 \frac{R}{2} \quad (2.2)$$

where κ_c and κ_p are constants.

Consider the same setup of each polariscope with the unstressed model. For each case, if the analyzer is rotated a counter-clockwise angle β , the intensity of the transmitted light emerging from the analyzer of a circular polariscope and a plane polariscope is, respectively, derived as

$$I_3 = \kappa_c \sin^2 \beta \quad (3.1)$$

and

$$I_4 = \kappa_p \sin^2 \beta \quad (3.2)$$

DIGITAL IMAGE PROCESSING

The whole field data of the intensity I_1, I_2, I_3 and I_4 were grabbed using a CCD camera connected to a frame grabber installed in a personal computer. Each intensity of I_1, I_2, I_3 and I_4 was converted into a gray level of Z_1, Z_2, Z_3 and Z_4 , respectively, by the digitizer and stored in the computer through the following relations:

$$Z_1 = \psi(I_1 + I_c)^\gamma = \psi_c \left(\sin^2 \frac{R}{2} + \phi_c \right)^\gamma \quad (4.1)$$

$$Z_2 = \psi(I_2 + I_p)^\gamma = \psi_p \left(\sin^2 2\alpha \sin^2 \frac{R}{2} + \phi_p \right)^\gamma \quad (4.2)$$

$$Z_3 = \psi(I_3 + I_c)^\gamma = \psi_c (\sin^2 \beta + \phi_c)^\gamma \quad (4.3)$$

$$Z_4 = \psi(I_4 + I_p)^\gamma = \psi_p (\sin^2 \beta + \phi_p)^\gamma \quad (4.4)$$

where

$$\psi_c = \psi \kappa_c^\gamma, \quad \phi_c = \frac{I_c}{\kappa_c}, \quad \psi_p = \psi \kappa_p^\gamma, \quad \phi_p = \frac{I_p}{\kappa_p} \quad (5)$$

in which ψ is the proportionality constant, γ is the log-linear slope of the CCD camera sensitivity and I_c and I_p are the background light intensity existing in the circular and plane polariscope experiments, respectively.

From Eqns (4.1) and (4.2) the isocromatic and isoclinic parameters R and α can be obtained, as long as the four constants $\psi_c, \phi_c, \psi_p, \phi_p$ and γ are known, through

$$R = 2 \arcsin \left[\left(\frac{Z_1}{\psi_c} \right)^{1/\gamma} - \phi_c \right]^{1/2} \quad (6.1)$$

$$\alpha = \pm \frac{1}{2} \arcsin \left\{ \left[\left(\frac{Z_2}{\psi_p} \right)^{1/\gamma} - \phi_p \right] \sin^{-2} \frac{R}{2} \right\}^{1/2} \quad (6.2)$$

The sign of α in Eqn (6.2) can be determined by one additional condition as described in the following. Another angle $\tilde{\alpha}$ of the principal strain direction with the polariscope rotated 22.5° counter clockwise is obtained using the same procedure as described above. Then it can be proved that if $0 \leq |\tilde{\alpha}| \leq 22.5$ the positive sign should be chosen for α , and if $22.5 < |\tilde{\alpha}| \leq 45$ the negative sign should be used.

CALIBRATION TECHNIQUE

To obtain the values for $\psi_c, \phi_c, \psi_p, \phi_p$ and γ the actual gray levels Z_3 and Z_4 were measured at various angles of β . Then the data of each pair of points (Z_3, β) and (Z_4, β) were substituted into Eqns (4.3) and (4.4) respectively to solve for $\psi_c, \phi_c, \psi_p, \phi_p$ and γ in a least square sense.

CALCULATION OF STRAINS AND STRESSES

In order to determine the three components of strains as well as stresses, at least one additional condition is needed other than R and α obtained from Eqns (6). In this work, the two force equilibrium equations constructed at each nodal point using FEM are employed as such additional conditions. And a least square method with constraints is applied to solve for this over determined solution over a chosen region.

FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

In the Finite Element analysis of a elasticity problem the force equilibrium relationship between the global nodal displacements and nodal forces is expressed as follows

$$K_{ij} U_j = F_i \quad (7)$$

where K_{ij} is the global stiffness matrix, U_j is a vector of the global nodal displacements and F_i is a vector of the global nodal forces.

To construct such system of nodal force equilibrium equations in a chosen region of the model in our experiments, some nodal forces F_i at the region boundary may not be obtained because lack of boundary conditions. At those boundary points the force equilibrium equations, therefore, can not be established. Other than such cases, the force equilibrium equations are obtained and used as constraints in the following least square method.

LEAST SQUARE METHOD

Two photoelastic data can be calculated with R and α at each nodal point of the Finite Element mesh using the following relations:

$$\varepsilon_x - \varepsilon_y = R\lambda(4\pi K)^{-1} \cos 2\alpha \quad (8.1)$$

$$\gamma_{xy} = R\lambda(4\pi K)^{-1} \sin 2\alpha \quad (8.1)$$

where ε_x , ε_y and γ_{xy} are the normal and shear strains in the x and y directions.

A least square method with constraints is applied to establish a system of equations to solve for the nodal displacements. The square difference between $\varepsilon_x - \varepsilon_y$ and γ_{xy} obtained from Eqns (8) and those derived from the FEM formulation over the chosen region is minimized with respect to each nodal displacement. In addition, the constraints of nodal force equilibrium equations as described in the previous section are enforced into the least square formulation by using Lagarange multipliers. Thus, a system of equations is formed in terms of nodal displacements and the Lagarange multipliers. Once the nodal displacements are solved, the strain and stress distribution over the entire region can be obtained with the FEM formulation

EXPERIMENTAL

FABRICATION OF 3D FABRICS AND COMPOSITES

High tenacity carbon fibers were used to fabricate 3D composites. The matrix system was based on the diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A, and comprised 100 parts by weight of GY260 epoxy resin, and 33 parts by weight of HT976 curing agent. In addition, 20 parts by weight of DER732 were added to toughen the epoxy resin.

3D fabrics composed of x-, y- and z-directional carbon rovings were fabricated in an orthogonal three-dimensional weaving loom. Fig. 1 shows a schematic of the orthogonal 3D fabric where the x- and y-directions correspond to two in-plane layer orientations. The z-direction or through-thickness fiber tows are interlocked with the in-plane layers using a knitting technique. In this study 12K filaments per tow were used for both x- and y-directions; the spacing between neighboring tows in the x-(or y-) direction was 6 mm. In the z-direction, 24K filaments were employed.

After fabrication the 3D fabrics were impregnated with epoxy resin and then heated in a vacuum oven according to a optimum cure cycle. The in-plane moduli of thus manufactured composites were measured as: $E_x = E_y = 40.0$ Gpa, $G_{xy} = 1.5$ Gpa and $\nu_{xy} = \nu_{yx} = 0.03$.

TESTING

The photoelastic experiment of a orthogonal 3D textile composite was carried out using a simple tension test. A photograph of the specimen is shown in Fig. 2. Loading was applied in the fiber direction which was the x-direction as indicated in Fig. 1. The dimension of the specimen was $250 \times 30 \times 3$ mm. On its surface was bonded with a 1 mm thick photoelastic coating of type PS-1, of which the strain-optical coefficient K was 0.15. A 030-Series reflection polariscope from the Measurements Group, INC was used in our experiments. A model 036 monochromator was employed to obtain monochromatic light of wavelength 575 nm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The values of R and α obtained for the simple tension test of a orthogonal 3D composite are shown in Figs. 3(a) and 3(b). In Fig. 3(a) the gray level at each pixel point represents the value of R , which varies over the entire region ranging from 0.5 to 1.4. Though, most of the values are close to 0.85 which is the theoretical value for the homogenized 3D composite. In Fig. 3(b) the gray level represents the absolute magnitude of α , which varies in a range of 0 to 15 degree.

Certainly, the variations of R and α are related to the non homogeneous structure of 3D composites. This fact can be observed from Figs. 3(a) and 3(b). In addition, the variations are also resulted from distortion of the fabric structure. This distortion, which is induced during preform fabrication and resin curing processes, is easily viewed in Fig. 2.

The strains ϵ_x , ϵ_y and γ_{xy} were solved using the least square method combining FEM over a interested region. This region spans across the width of the specimen and extends between the two lines as indicated in Fig. 3. Totally 60 square elements were used for the mesh. Thus obtained values of ϵ_x , ϵ_y and γ_{xy} on a horizontal line across the specimen were plotted with

respect to distance from the left edge of the specimen as shown in Fig. 4. In addition, the values of $\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2$ calculated directly from R on the same line were also plotted in Fig. 4.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of orthogonal 3D fabric.

Fig. 2 A photograph of the specimen surface.

As shown in Fig. 4 the curve of the dominant strain ε_x is much more smooth than that of $\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2$. This smoothing effect is the averaging result induced by enforcing force equilibrium equations over the region using the homogenized composite properties. It is also noticed that the values of ε_x calculated over the region are close to the theoretical value 2.52×10^{-4} for the homogenized composite material. Such results indicate that this analysis approach for orthogonal 3D composites is quite successful. Though the values of ε_x as well as $\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_2$ are found to increase with distance, this increasing trend is believed to be the result of non uniform material properties across the specimen with due to imperfection of the fabric structure. In addition, the correct values of ε_y are acquired as shown in Fig. 4. However, the values of γ_{xy} are not as small as expected. This is because the 3D composite is soft in shearing and it was indeed loaded with shear force due to distortion of the fabric structure.

Fig. 3 The distributions of R and α of which the values are expressed with gray levels in (a) and (b), respectively.

Fig. 4 Plots of $\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2$, ϵ_x , ϵ_y and γ_{xy} v.s. distance from left edge of the specimen along a horizontal line.

CONCLUSION

A computer-aided photoelastic analysis method for orthogonal 3D textile composites is presented. This method has been used to successfully extract the photoelastic data and strain and stress distribution for a simple tension experiment. The strain and stress distributions obtained not only satisfy all the elasticity field equations for the homogenized composite but also best fit the photoelastic data in an averaging sense. Therefore, there is no error accumulation in strain

and stress calculation as that happens in the shear difference method. In addition, any error induced in the photoelastic experiments can be eliminated or reduced because of enforcement of elasticity field equations and whole-field photoelastic data fitting.

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